

Photo-bromination of *m*-Nitrobenzylidene Malonic Ester. Part II.

By

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In a previous paper (*This Journal*, 1927, 4, 375) the photo-bromination of *m*-nitrobenzylidene malonic ester in carbon tetrachloride solutions has been studied. The present investigation deals with the same reaction with carbon disulphide as the solvent. It might be mentioned at the outset that the main features of this investigation are exactly analogous to those previously obtained. As before, a photo-chemical equilibrium ensues which is given by *Dibromide* / *Bromine* × *Ester*, and which again is determined by temperature and intensity of radiation. The equilibrium once attained does not change when the system in equilibrium is transferred to darkness.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The methods of investigation were the same as before. The incident radiation was measured by means of a Moll thermopile and a Moll galvanometer. The dark reaction was found to be negligible there being practically no reaction in course of 24 hours.

Tables I-IV indicate the result of the experiment on the determination of the point of equilibrium.

TABLE I.

Intensity of light (488.5 μ)—160/12 Hefners-at-100 cm.

Temperature 32°.

Initial conc. of ester : gm. mol./litre.	Initial conc. of bromine : gm. mol./litre.	Equilibrium conc. of Br : gm. mol./litre.	<u>Dibromide</u> Bromine × Ester.
0150	0150	00875	81.6
0100	0160	0066	79.2
0087	00885	00605	78.0
0060	0049	00875	80.1
0150	0093	00580	75.8
0100	01495	01045	78.9
		Mean	78.0

TABLE II.

Intensity of incident light ($488.5 \mu\mu$)—77/12 Hefners-at-100 cm.Temperature 32° .

Initial conc. of ester : gm. mol./litre.	Initial conc. of Br : gm. mol./litre	Equilibrium conc. of Br : gm. mol./litre.	Dibromide
			Bromine $\times$ Ester.
'0150	'0152	'0102	49.0
'0100	'0097	'0072	48.8
'0067	'0067	'00525	52.4
'0067	'00955	'00765	51.6
'0100	'00725	'00525	49.0
'0050	'0050	'00415	49.7
		Mean	50.0

TABLE III.

Intensity of light ($488.5 \mu\mu$)—160/12 Hefners-at-100 cm.Temperature 27° .

Initial conc. of ester : gm. mol./litre.	Initial conc. of Br : gm. mol./litre.	Equilibrium conc. of Br : gm. mol./litre.	Dibromide
			Bromine $\times$ Ester.
'0150	'01495	'0094	62.4
'0102	'0096	'0067	59.3
'0067	'0065	'00505	54.7
'0050	'0049	'00395	59.4
		Mean	58.9

TABLE IV.

Intensity of incident light ($488.5 \mu\mu$)—77/12 Hefners-at-100 cm.Temperature 27° .

Initial conc. of ester : gm. mol./litre.	Initial conc. of bromine : gm. mol./litre.	Equilibrium conc. of Br : gm. mol./litre.	Dibromide
			Bromine $\times$ Ester .
'0150	'01410	'0100	38.2
'0100	'0097	'0075	37.6
'0067	'0071	'00585	38.9
'0005	'0049	'0042	36.2
		Mean	37.7

Comparison of Tables I and II and Tables III and IV again brings out the interesting fact that the ratio of the equilibrium constants 1.55 ($78/50$ and $59/78$) is equal to the ratio of the square root of the corresponding incident intensities $\sqrt{160/77} = 1.45$.

Experiments on the Rate of Bromination.

In this investigation the initial concentrations of ester and bromine were not always identical and the velocity of bromination should, therefore, be given by

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k_1(a-x)(b-x) - k_2x \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where a and b represent the initial concentrations of ester and bromine respectively.

Integration of this equation gives

$$k_1 = \frac{1}{t} \frac{1}{c_2 - c_1} \left[\log \frac{c_2 - x}{c_2} - \log \frac{c_1 - x}{c_1} \right]$$

where c_1 and c_2 are the roots of the equation,

$$ab - x \left(a + b + \frac{k_2}{k_1} \right) + x^2 = 0$$

i. e., c_1 is the equilibrium value of x , and $c_2 = \frac{ab}{c_1}$

when $a=b$, the roots are

$$a + \lambda + \sqrt{\lambda(2a + \lambda)} \quad \text{and} \quad a + \lambda - \sqrt{\lambda(2a + \lambda)} \quad \text{where} \quad \frac{1}{2\lambda} = \frac{k_2}{k_1},$$

and in that case

$$k_1 = \frac{1}{t} \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\lambda(2a+x)}} \left[\log \frac{a + \lambda - x + \sqrt{\lambda(2a + \lambda)}}{a + \lambda - x - \sqrt{\lambda(2a + \lambda)}} - \log \frac{a + \lambda + \sqrt{\lambda(2a + \lambda)}}{a + \lambda - \sqrt{\lambda(2a + \lambda)}} \right] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

which is the equation used in Part I.

Tables V to VIII indicate the typical results and Table IX gives a summary of all the measurements. One c. c. of the reaction mixture was titrated throughout.

TABLE V (SERIES A, TABLE IX).

Intensity of incident light (488.5 $\mu\mu$)—160/12 Hefners-at-100 cm.
 Conc. of ester—0.0150 M. Conc. of bromine—0.0096 M.

Temperature 32°.			
Time in minutes.	N/500 bromine.	k_1	Mean k_1
0	9.60 c. c. *	...	
60	8.60	.134	
120	7.85	.134	.136
210	6.90	.138	

TABLE VI (SERIES B, TABLE IX).

Intensity of incident light (488.5 $\mu\mu$)—77/12 Hefners-at-100 cm.

Temperature 32°.

Conc. of ester—0.0067 M.		Conc. of bromine—0.0067 M.	
Time in mins.	N/500 bromine.	k_1	Mean k_1
0	6.7 c. c.		
60	6.45	.102	
120	6.25	.102	.102
210	6.0	.101	

TABLE VII (SERIES C, TABLE IX).

Intensity of incident light (488.5 $\mu\mu$)—160/12 Hefners-at-100 cm.

Temperature 27°.

Conc. of ester—0.0150 M.		Conc. of bromine—0.01495 M.	
Time in mins.	N/500 bromine.	k_1	Mean k_1
0	14.95 c. c.	...	
60	13.8	.097	
120	12.9	.098	.100
210	11.75	.106	

TABLE VIII (SERIES D, TABLE IX).

Intensity of incident light (489.5 $\mu\mu$)—77/12 Hefners-at-100 cm.

Temperature 27°.

Conc. of ester—0.0150 M. Conc. of bromine—0.0149 M.

Time in mins	N/500 bromine	k_1	Mean k_1
0	14.1 c.c.		
60	13.3	.0706	
120	12.7	.0684	.0700
180	11.7	.0712	

TABLE IX.

Series	Intensity of radiation.	Temperature.	Initial conc. of ester.	Initial conc. of Br.	Mean k_1
A	160/12 Hefners-at -100 cm.	32°	·0150 M	·0150 M	·127
			·010 M	·0101 M	·137
			·0067 M	·00685 M	·136
			·0150 M	·0096 M	·138
			·010 M	·01495 M	·127
B	77/12 Hefners-at -100 cm.	32°	·0150 M	·0152 M	·0924
			·010 M	·0097 M	·0900
			·0067 M	·0067 M	·102
			·0067 M	·00955 M	·0900
C	160/12 Hefners-at -100 cm.	27°	·0150 M	·01495 M	·100
			·0102 M	·0096 M	·0922
			·0067 M	·0065 M	·1027
D	77/12 Hefners-at -100 cm.	27°	·0150 M	·0140 M	·0700
			·010 M	·0097 M	·0597
			·0067 M	·0071 M	·0672

It will be seen that, as before, intensity of radiation and temperature remaining constant, the value of k_1 remains the same.

Temperature Coefficient of k_1 and k_2 .

Comparison of series A and C and Series B and D of measurements gives the values

$$\left(\frac{\cdot133}{\cdot0983}\right)^{\frac{1}{5}^{\circ}} \text{ i.e. } 1\cdot8 \text{ and } \left(\frac{\cdot096}{\cdot0659}\right)^{\frac{1}{5}^{\circ}}$$

i.e. 2·1 for the temperature coefficient of k_1 . We can now calculate the temperature coefficient of k_2 . Let x be the temperature coefficient of k_2 for 5°C (32°—27°).

$$\text{Now at } 27^{\circ} \text{ from Table III, } K_1 \left(\frac{k_1}{k_2}\right) = 59\cdot0$$

K_2 , the equilibrium constant at 32° = 78·0 (vide Table I).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Again } K_2 &= \frac{k_1 \text{ at } 27^{\circ} \times 1\cdot4}{k_2 \text{ at } 27^{\circ} \times x} \\ &= K_1 \times \frac{1\cdot4}{x} \quad \text{or } x = 1\cdot06. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the temperature coefficient of k_2 for 10°C

$$= 1\cdot06^{\frac{1}{5}^{\circ}} = 1\cdot12 \text{ a value less than that for } k_1.$$

Application of Einstein's Law.

The reverse reaction during the first 60 minutes will not be very great and we can approximately calculate the quantum efficiency. Taking the results in Table VII, since the absorption of the incident radiation ($488.4 \mu\mu$) by bromine solutions in carbon disulphide employed can be taken to be complete, number of quanta absorbed per square cm per second

$$= \frac{160}{12} \times 900 \frac{488 \times 10^{-7}}{3 \times 10^{10}} \times \frac{1}{6.5 \times 10^{-17}}$$

$$= 3.0 \times 10^{15} \text{ quanta per sq. cm. per sec.}$$

The change is 1.15 c.c. N/500 bromine per c.c. in 60 minutes; hence no. of mols transformed per sq. cm. per sec. $\times$ depth of reaction vessel

$$= \frac{1.15}{1000 \times 1000} \times \frac{1}{60 \times 60} \times 6.1 \times 10^5 \times 1.5 \text{ (depth of reaction vessel)}$$

$$= 0.28 \times 10^{15} \text{ mols per sq. cm. p. r sec.}$$

Thus about 11 quanta are necessary for the transformation of one molecule. When calculated, the quantum efficiency in all cases comes out to be less than unity.

Theoretical.

Since the first part of the paper was published, a paper by Berthoud and Nicolet on the photo-bromination of the nitrile of α -phenylcinnamic acid has appeared in *Helvetica Chimica Acta* (1927, 10, 417). These authors maintain that the velocity of photo-bromination in this case is proportional to the concentration of bromine and is independent of the concentration of the nitrile, while the velocity of the reverse decomposition is proportional directly to the concentration of the dibromide and inversely to the concentration of the nitrile. They thus obtain the following equation.

$$\frac{d[\text{ABr}_2]}{dt} = k_1[\text{Br}_2] - k_2 \frac{[\text{ABr}_2]}{A} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

which gives for zero velocity, when photochemical stationary state has been reached, the mass action expression,

$$\frac{[A][Br_2]}{[ABr_2]} = K$$

This constant is obviously independent of the intensity of illumination.

It is clear that our experiments on the photo-bromination of *m*-nitrobenzylidene malonic ester yield results which must be interpreted in a different way. In the first place, the equilibrium constant has been found to depend on the intensity of illumination, being in fact proportional approximately to the square root of the intensity of incident light. Again as the following measurements in carbon tetrachloride solutions (*vide* Table X) will show, the velocity of photobromination at the initial stage of the reaction, where the effect of the reverse reaction can be neglected without involving much error, is not only proportional to the concentration of bromine but increases very considerably as the concentration of the ester creases.

TABLE X.

Temperature 32°.

Conc. of ester	...	·0040M	·0067M	·0067M	·0133M
Conc. of bromine	...	·00815M	·0080M	·00665M	·0067M
Change of Br conc. in first 20 mins. in c. c. N/500 sol. per c. c. of mixture.		0·35 c.c.	0·65 c.c.	0·50 c.c.	0·75 c.c.

It is evident that equation (3) as given by Berthoud is not applicable to this reaction. It appears almost impossible to ignore the fact that whenever photobromination does not proceed to completion the concentrations of the unsaturated molecule and the dibromide affect very considerably the velocity of bromination or reverse decomposition. In the particular reaction we have studied, the results can be expressed within certain ranges of concentration by the equation,

$$\frac{d[ABr_2]}{dt} = k_1[A][Br_2] - K_2 \sqrt{I}[ABr_2]$$

Influence of Solvent: It will be seen by referring to Tables III and IV of the previous paper (*loc. cit.*) and Tables II and IV of this

paper that for the same intensity of incident radiation the value of the equilibrium constant in carbon tetrachloride solutions is about seven times the value of the constant in carbon disulphide solutions. The velocity of bromination in carbon tetrachloride is also about seven times the corresponding value for carbon disulphide solutions (*vide* Tables V and VI of Part I and Tables X-XIII of this paper). Thus in carbon disulphide solutions the reverse reaction, *i.e.*, the decomposition of the dibromide proceeds further and more quickly than in carbon tetrachloride solutions.

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